

MAGISTRLAR CERTIFICATE

OF ACHIEVEMENT

... PROUDLY ...
PRESENTED TO

Allaboyeva Zebuniso Baxrom qizi

POLYSEMY IN PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES

WEBSITE: WWW.REANDPUB.UZ

EMAIL: INFO@REANDPUB.UZ

2023/MAY

